

A Hybrid AHP–WSM–TOPSIS Decision Framework for Optimal Gas Turbine Retrofit Selection under Conflicting Thermo-Economic Objectives

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Abstract

Gas turbine retrofit planning involves complex trade-offs among thermodynamic performance, economic viability, and environmental impact, given conflicting objectives. Conventional retrofit studies often emphasize isolated performance indicators or rely on deterministic decision frameworks, limiting their applicability to real-world investment and operational planning. This study presents an integrated thermo-economic and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) framework for optimal selection of gas turbine retrofits, using the Omotosho gas turbine power plant as a real-world case study.

Three advanced retrofit configurations—incorporating inlet air cooling, exhaust gas regeneration, heat-recovery steam generation (HRSG)-based steam injection, additional turbine stages, and dual combustion chambers — are modelled and evaluated against the baseline simple-cycle plant. Detailed thermodynamic simulations are performed using ASPEN HYSYS, while long-term economic performance is assessed over a 20-year operating horizon. To address conflicting objectives, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is used to determine criterion weights, which are integrated into the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for retrofit ranking.

Results indicate that all retrofit configurations significantly outperform the baseline plant. The MGTP-1 configuration consistently demonstrates superior performance, achieving the highest thermal efficiency (47.44%), the most excellent net power output (157.08 MW), the lowest specific fuel consumption, and the highest net economic benefit. Both WSM and TOPSIS rank MGTP-1 as the optimal retrofit option, with sensitivity analysis confirming its robustness across varying operating conditions.

The proposed framework provides a transparent, data-driven decision-support tool for identifying economically viable and environmentally sustainable gas turbine retrofit strategies.

Keywords: *Gas turbine retrofit, Thermo-economic analysis, Multi-criteria decision-making, Power plant optimisation, Energy system sustainability.*

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Introduction

Gas turbine power plants remain a cornerstone of modern electricity generation due to their high operational flexibility, rapid start-up capability, compact footprint, and compatibility with both conventional fossil fuels and emerging low-carbon energy systems such as hydrogen blending and renewable hybridization. (Burnes, Saxena, & Kurz, 2022; Colbertaldo, Guandalini, Crespi, & Campanari, 2021; Harper et al., 2024; Parsania et al., 2024; Varghese, Dalvi, Narula, & Webster, 2021; Villatoro, McDonell, Hu, & Ayers, 2022; Wu, Wang, & Liu, 2020; Zeng, Xu, Zhang, & Bai, 2023). In many developing and emerging economies, gas turbines constitute a substantial share of installed generation capacity and play a critical role in grid stability, peak-load management, and emergency power supply (Colbertaldo et al., 2021; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni, Giugno, & Sorce, 2020; Varghese et al., 2021). However, a significant portion of the global gas turbine fleet is currently operating below its design performance owing to aging infrastructure, component degradation, harsh ambient conditions, and suboptimal cycle configurations (Mzad & Bennour, 2024; Padhi & Pattanayak, 2023; Ricci et al., 2021; Umyshev et al., 2023). These factors lead to reduced thermal efficiency, increased fuel consumption, and elevated greenhouse gas emissions (Abubaker et al., 2024; Mzad & Bennour, 2024; Padhi & Pattanayak, 2023; Ricci et al., 2021).

Replacing aging gas turbine units with new-generation technologies is often economically prohibitive, particularly in regions facing capital constraints, growing electricity demand, and supply deficits (Esfandiari, Pourfayaz, Kasaeian, & Gholami, 2024; Hai, El-Shafay, Goyal, Alshahri, & Almujiabah, 2023; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020). Consequently, retrofitting existing gas turbine power plants has emerged as a cost-effective and strategically attractive pathway to enhance performance,

reduce environmental impact, and extend plant lifetime while minimizing capital investment (Abubaker et al., 2024; Fajardo, Barreto, Yabrudy, & Piña-Martinez, 2023; Hohloch et al., 2025; Hughes et al., 2023; Jia, Liu, Li, & Jiang, 2023). Retrofit strategies such as inlet air cooling, exhaust gas regeneration, steam or water injection, intercooling, reheating, additional turbine stages, and multi-combustor arrangements have been widely investigated and have been shown to significantly improve power output and thermal efficiency, particularly under hot-climate operating condition (Abed et al., 2024; Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Bağ, Ziolkowski, Frost, & Drosińska-Komor, 2023; Esfandiari et al., 2024; Fajardo et al., 2023; Hai et al., 2023; Owebor et al., 2022).

Among these technologies, inlet air cooling mitigates the adverse impact of high ambient temperatures on compressor mass flow rate (Esfandiari et al., 2024; Mzad & Bennour, 2024; Padhi & Pattanayak, 2023). Regeneration enables the recovery of exhaust heat to reduce fuel demand (Fajardo et al., 2023; Hai et al., 2023; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020), steam injection increases turbine mass flow and power output (Esfandiari et al., 2024; Fajardo et al., 2023; Hai et al., 2023), while extended expansion through additional turbine stages enhances energy extraction from high-enthalpy exhaust gases (Ge et al., 2019; Ravelli, 2025; S.O. Abduljabbar, Hagraş, & Magadmy, 2020). When appropriately integrated, these modifications can transform a simple-cycle gas turbine into a highly efficient and economically competitive power generation system (Fajardo et al., 2023; Hai et al., 2023).

Despite the demonstrated benefits of individual retrofit technologies, selecting an optimal retrofit configuration remains a complex engineering and investment decision problem (Burnes et al., 2022; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020; Varghese et al., 2021).

Retrofit options often improve specific performance indicators at the expense of others. For example, higher thermal efficiency may be accompanied by increased capital cost or system complexity, while emission-reduction measures may reduce net power output or fuel flexibility (Hai et al., 2023; Kazemiani-Najafabadi & Amiri Rad, 2020; Umyshev et al., 2023; Varghese et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2025). As a result, retrofit planning inherently involves multiple, often conflicting thermo-economic and environmental objectives, rendering single-criterion optimization approaches inadequate for real-world decision-making (Kumar et al., 2017).

To address these trade-offs, multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) techniques have been increasingly adopted in energy system analysis (Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Babahammou, Merabet, & Miles, 2024; Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022; Siksnyte-Butkiene, Zavadskas, & Streimikiene, 2020). Methods such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Weighted Sum Method (WSM), and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) provide structured frameworks for simultaneously evaluating multiple performance indicators and ranking competing alternatives (Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022; Siksnyte-Butkiene et al., 2020). In gas turbine applications, MCDM approaches have been employed to support decisions related to technology selection, fuel switching, performance enhancement, and sustainability assessment (Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022; Siksnyte-Butkiene et al., 2020; Strantzali & Aravossis, 2016).

However, three critical limitations persist in the existing literature. First, many gas turbine retrofit studies focus primarily on isolated thermodynamic or economic indicators, such as efficiency improvement, power augmentation, or payback period, without integrating these results into a comprehensive decision-support framework (Esfandiari et al., 2024; Fajardo et al., 2023; Padhi & Pattanayak, 2023; Umyshev et al., 2023), such approaches risk recommending technically superior solutions that may be

economically unattractive or operationally impractical (Mohammadi, Ahmadi, Bidi, Ghazvini, & Ming, 2018; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020).

Second, although MCDM techniques are increasingly applied, a large proportion of studies rely on subjective or fixed criterion weights, often derived solely from expert judgment and not subjected to systematic validation or sensitivity assessment (Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Cinelli, Kadziński, Gonzalez, & Słowiński, 2020; Owebor et al., 2022; Siksnyte-Butkiene et al., 2020). This introduces bias into the ranking process and limits the transparency and reproducibility of decision outcomes, particularly for high-stakes infrastructure investments (Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022).

Third, and most importantly, many MCDM-based retrofit studies lack strong coupling with high-fidelity plant-level simulations and real operational data (Harper et al., 2024; Mzad & Bennour, 2024; Parsania et al., 2024; Ricci et al., 2021). Instead, simplified or hypothetical datasets are frequently employed, reducing the practical relevance of the results for actual power plant operators, investors, and policymakers (Gülen, 2019; Harper et al., 2024; Parsania et al., 2024; Ricci et al., 2021). Moreover, sensitivity analyses are often limited to thermodynamic performance trends, while the robustness of final decision rankings under varying operating conditions remains largely unexplored (Jia et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022; Varghese et al., 2021).

Based on the foregoing review, there is a clear need for an integrated, data-driven decision framework that combines detailed thermo-economic modelling of real gas turbine power plants with transparent and systematic multi-criteria decision analysis. There is limited work that simultaneously:

1. Evaluates multiple advanced gas turbine retrofit configurations using validated process simulation tools under realistic operating conditions.
2. Integrates long-term economic performance with thermodynamic and

environmental indicators in a unified assessment framework.

3. Applies well-established MCDM techniques such as WSM and TOPSIS consistently and comparatively to resolve conflicting objectives; and

4. Utilizes real plant data to enhance the credibility, robustness, and practical relevance of retrofit decisions.

To address these gaps, the present study develops a comprehensive thermo-economic and MCDM-based framework for optimal selection of gas turbine retrofits, using the Omotosho gas turbine power plant as a real-world case study. Three advanced retrofit configurations incorporating inlet air cooling, exhaust gas regeneration, HRSG-based steam injection, additional turbine stages, and dual combustion chambers are modelled and simulated using ASPEN HYSYS (Ibrahim et al., 2017; Umyshev et al., 2023). Their performance is evaluated based on thermal efficiency, power output, fuel consumption, emission intensity, and long-term economic indicators over a 20-year operating horizon (Hai et al., 2023; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020).

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is employed to derive criterion weights, which are subsequently integrated into both the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and TOPSIS to rank retrofit alternatives and support transparent decision-making (Al-Rashed & Afrand, 2021; Kumar et al., 2017; Owebor et al., 2022; Siksnelyte-Butkiene et al., 2020). A sensitivity analysis is conducted to assess the robustness of performance trends and the stability of rankings under varying operating conditions (Jia et al., 2023; Owebor et al., 2022; Varghese et al., 2021).

By combining high-fidelity plant-level simulation with structured multi-criteria decision analysis, this study provides a robust, transparent, and practically applicable decision-support framework for gas turbine retrofit planning. The proposed methodology offers valuable guidance for power plant operators, investors, and policymakers seeking cost-effective and environmentally sustainable strategies to enhance the performance of

existing gas turbine assets (Abubaker et al., 2024; Owebor et al., 2022; Umyshev et al., 2023; Vannoni et al., 2020).

Case Study Description and System Overview

Description of the Omotosho Gas Turbine Power Plant

The Omotosho power station is a large-scale gas-fired power plant located in southwestern Nigeria. It represents a typical industrial heavy-duty gas turbine installation widely deployed across many developing economies for baseload and peak-load electricity generation. The plant operates under tropical climatic conditions characterized by high ambient temperatures and humidity, which significantly influence compressor performance, mass flow rate, and overall cycle efficiency.

The reference unit considered in this study is a heavy-duty open-cycle gas turbine operating on the Brayton cycle and fuelled with natural gas. The plant comprises an axial-flow air compressor, a combustion chamber, and an expansion turbine that drives an electrical generator. In the baseline configuration, turbine exhaust gases are discharged to the atmosphere.

Like many gas turbine plants operating in hot climates, the Omotosho plant experiences substantial performance degradation during periods of high ambient temperature, resulting in reduced power output, increased specific fuel consumption, and elevated operating costs. These characteristics make the plant an ideal candidate for retrofit-based performance enhancement.

The plant was selected as a case study due to the availability of operational data, its representativeness of industrial gas turbine installations in tropical regions, and its strategic importance within the national electricity grid.

Baseline Plant Configuration

The process diagram of the baseline plant configuration in Aspen Hysys is presented in Appendix A, Figure 13. The baseline system is a conventional open-cycle gas turbine power plant operating without waste heat recovery or inlet air conditioning. Ambient air enters the

compressor, where it is compressed to the required pressure level before entering the combustion chamber. Natural gas is injected and combusted at constant pressure, and the high-temperature combustion products expand through the turbine, driving a generator and converting mechanical power into electricity. The major components of the baseline configuration include the air compressor, combustion chamber, turbine, and electric generator.

The exhaust gases are released directly to the atmosphere without energy recovery, resulting in a significant loss of available thermal energy.

Retrofit System Configurations

To enhance the performance of the baseline plant, three advanced retrofit configurations were developed and evaluated. These configurations represent progressively increasing levels of thermodynamic integration and system complexity.

MGTP-1 Configuration

MGTP-1 integrates four key retrofit technologies:

1. Inlet air cooling system to reduce compressor inlet temperature and increase air density.
2. Exhaust gas regenerator to recover waste heat and preheat compressed air.
3. Heat recovery steam generator (HRSG) for steam production.
4. Steam injection into the combustion chamber and an additional low-pressure turbine stage for extended expansion.

The process diagram of MGTP-1 in Aspen Hysys is presented in Appendix A, Figure 14. This configuration effectively transforms the simple-cycle gas turbine into a highly efficient steam-injected regenerative cycle with extended expansion capability.

MGTP-2 Configuration

MGTP-2 incorporates:

1. Inlet air cooling
2. Exhaust gas regeneration

3. HRSG-based steam injection
4. Dual combustion chambers arranged in series

The process diagram of MGTP-2 in Aspen Hysys is presented in Appendix A, Figure 15. The second combustion chamber reheats the working fluid between turbine expansion stages, thereby increasing the average temperature at which heat is supplied to the cycle. This approach enhances power output but increases fuel consumption and system complexity.

MGTP-3 Configuration

MGTP-3 represents the most advanced and integrated configuration, combining:

1. Inlet air cooling
2. Exhaust gas regeneration
3. HRSG-based steam injection
4. Dual turbine stages
5. Dual combustion chambers

The process diagram of MGTP-1 in Aspen Hysys is presented in Appendix A, Figure 16. This configuration maximizes energy recovery and power augmentation but entails higher capital costs, increased auxiliary consumption, and greater operational complexity.

Modelling Approach and Boundary Conditions

All plant configurations were modelled using ASPEN HYSYS version 11 under steady-state conditions. The simulation environment was configured to represent actual industrial gas turbine operation using validated thermodynamic property models and component efficiencies consistent with manufacturer specifications and published literature.

The following modelling assumptions were adopted:

1. Steady-flow operation
2. Ideal gas behaviour for air and combustion products
3. Complete combustion of natural gas
4. Negligible heat loss to the environment

5. Constant isentropic efficiencies for compressor and turbine
6. Negligible pressure losses in piping and heat exchangers

The Peng–Robinson equation of state was used to evaluate properties. The natural gas composition was defined using typical pipeline-quality gas.

Input Data and Operating Conditions

The baseline plant and retrofit configurations were simulated under identical operating conditions to ensure consistency and comparability. The key operating parameters include:

1. Ambient temperature: representative tropical design condition
2. Ambient pressure: site elevation condition
3. Compressor pressure ratio: industrial heavy-duty turbine range
4. Turbine inlet temperature: manufacturer-rated value
5. Compressor and turbine isentropic efficiencies: based on industrial performance data
6. Generator efficiency: standard utility-scale value

Fuel lower heating value (LHV) and emission factors were selected in accordance with standard natural gas specifications.

Model Verification and Consistency Check

The baseline plant model was first developed and verified against typical industrial gas turbine performance ranges reported in the literature and manufacturer data. Key output parameters, including thermal efficiency, specific fuel consumption, heat rate, and exhaust temperature, were checked to ensure consistency with expected values for heavy-duty open-cycle gas turbines operating under similar ambient conditions.

The retrofit configurations were then constructed incrementally from the validated baseline model. Mass and energy balance closure was verified for all system components, and

convergence was achieved under all operating conditions considered in the study.

The thermodynamic trends observed across retrofit configurations were also cross-checked against published studies on regenerative, steam-injected, and reheated gas turbine cycles, ensuring physical consistency and model reliability.

Research Framework

The methodological framework developed in this study integrates thermodynamic process simulation, life-cycle economic assessment, and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) to identify the optimal gas turbine retrofit configuration under conflicting performance objectives. The framework is designed to provide a transparent, data-driven, and practically applicable decision-support tool for retrofit planning of existing gas turbine power plants.

The overall framework consists of four sequential and interconnected stages:

1. Thermodynamic modelling of the baseline and retrofit configurations using high-fidelity process simulation.
2. Life-cycle economic evaluation based on long-term cost–benefit analysis.
3. Multi-criteria decision analysis using the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), with criterion weights derived from the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP); and
4. Sensitivity analysis to assess the robustness of system performance and ranking stability under varying operating conditions.

A schematic representation of the integrated thermo-economic and MCDM framework is shown in Figure 1. The framework ensures consistency and comparability across all retrofit alternatives by applying identical boundary conditions, modelling assumptions, and evaluation criteria.

Figure 1. Integrated Thermo-Economic and MCDM Framework for Gas Turbine Retrofit Selection

Thermodynamic Modelling

Thermodynamic performance of the baseline and retrofit configurations was evaluated using ASPEN HYSYS version 11, a widely validated industrial process simulation platform for power generation and energy systems. Steady-state mass and energy balance equations were applied to all components under the following assumptions: steady-flow operation, ideal-gas behaviour for air and combustion products, negligible changes in kinetic and potential energy, constant isentropic efficiencies for turbomachinery, and complete combustion in the combustion chambers.

The Peng–Robinson equation of state was employed to estimate properties, and component efficiencies were selected based on manufacturer specifications and published literature.

Energy Balance

For a steady-flow control volume, the first law of thermodynamics is expressed as:

$$\dot{Q} - \dot{W} = \sum \dot{m}_{out} h_{out} - \sum \dot{m}_{in} h_{in} \quad (1)$$

Where \dot{Q} is the heat transfer rate (kW), \dot{W} is the work transfer rate (kW), \dot{m} is the mass flow rate of the working fluid (kg/s), and h is the specific enthalpy (kJ/kg).

Compressor Model

The compressor pressure ratio is defined as:

$$r_p = \frac{P_2}{P_1} \quad (2)$$

Where r_p is compressor pressure ratio, P_2 is compressor outlet pressure (Pa or bar) and P_1 is compressor inlet pressure (Pa or bar).

The isentropic efficiency of the compressor is given by:

$$\eta_c = \frac{T_{2s} - T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \quad (3)$$

Where η_c is the compressor isentropic efficiency, T_{2s} is the temperature at the compressor outlet under isentropic conditions (K), T_2 is the actual temperature at the compressor outlet (K), and T_1 is the temperature at the compressor inlet (K).

The compressor work is calculated as:

$$W_c = \dot{m}_a C_{p,a} (T_2 - T_1) \quad (4)$$

Where W_c is compressor power consumption (kW), \dot{m}_a is the mass flow rate of air (kg/s), T_2 is compressor outlet temperature (K), T_1 is compressor inlet temperature (K), and $C_{p,a}$ is the specific heat capacity of air.

Combustion Chamber Model

The energy balance across the combustion chamber is expressed as:

$$\dot{m}_a h_2 + \dot{m}_f LHV = (\dot{m}_a + \dot{m}_f) h_3 \quad (5)$$

Where \dot{m}_a is air mass flow rate (kg/s), h_2 is the enthalpy of compressed air entering the combustor (kJ/kg), \dot{m}_f is fuel mass flow rate (kg/s), LHV is the lower heating value of fuel (kJ/kg), and h_3 is the enthalpy of combustion gases at combustor exit (kJ/kg)

The fuel–air ratio is defined as:

$$f = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{\dot{m}_a} \quad (6)$$

Where f is Fuel–air ratio, \dot{m}_f is fuel mass flow rate (kg/s) and \dot{m}_a is air mass flow rate (kg/s),

Turbine Model

The turbine isentropic efficiency is given by:

$$\eta_t = \frac{T_3 - T_4}{T_3 - T_{4s}} \quad (7)$$

Where η_t The isentropic efficiency of a turbine is T_3 is turbine inlet temperature (K), T_4 is the turbine inlet temperature (K) and T_{4s} is the

turbine exit temperature under isentropic expansion (K).

The turbine work output is calculated as:

$$W_t = \dot{m}_g C_{p,g} (T_3 - T_4) \quad (8)$$

Where W_t is turbine power output (kW), \dot{m}_g is the mass flow rate of combustion gases (kg/s), $C_{p,g}$ is the specific heat capacity of a gas, T_3 is the turbine inlet temperature (K) and T_4 is the turbine inlet temperature (K).

Net Power Output and Performance Indicators

The net power output is expressed as:

$$W_{net} = W_t - W_c \quad (9)$$

Where W_{net} is the net power output of the plant (kW), W_t is turbine power output (kW) and W_c is compressor power consumption (kW)

Thermal efficiency is defined as:

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{W_{net}}{\dot{m}_f * LHV} \quad (10)$$

Where η_{th} is thermal efficiency, W_{net} is the net power output of the plant (kW), \dot{m}_f is fuel mass flow rate (kg/s), and LHV is the lower heating value of fuel (kJ/kg).

Specific fuel consumption (SFC) is calculated as:

$$SFC = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{W_{net}} \quad (11)$$

Where SFC is specific fuel consumption, \dot{m}_f is fuel mass flow rate (kg/s) and W_{net} is the net power output of the plant (kW).

Heat rate is expressed as:

$$HR = \frac{3600}{\eta_{th}} \quad (12)$$

Where HR is the heat rate and η_{th} is thermal efficiency.

Emission rate is estimated as:

$$Emission\ Rate = Emission\ Factor * SFC \quad (13)$$

Economic Analysis

A life-cycle cost–benefit analysis was conducted over a 20-year operating horizon, consistent with standard practice in power plant investment evaluation. The economic assessment incorporates capital expenditure (CAPEX), operation and maintenance (O&M) costs, fuel costs, and electricity sales revenue.

The total cost is calculated as:

$$C_{total} = C_{cap} + \sum_{t=1}^n (C_{O\&M} + C_{fuel}) \quad (14)$$

Where C_{total} is the total cost (USD), C_{cap} is capital cost (USD), $C_{O\&M}$ is the operation and maintenance cost (USD) and C_{fuel} is fuel cost (USD).

Total revenue is calculated as:

$$R_{total} = P_e * E \quad (15)$$

Where R_{total} is total revenue, P_e is the electricity selling price (USD/kWh) and E is electricity generated (kWh).

Net benefit is defined as:

$$NB = R_{total} - C_{total} \quad (16)$$

Where NB is net economic benefit (USD), R_{total} is the total revenue and C_{total} is the total cost (USD).

The Benefit–Cost Ratio (BCR) is calculated as:

$$BCR = \frac{R_{total}}{C_{total}} \quad (17)$$

Where BCR is the Benefit–Cost Ratio, R_{total} is the total revenue and C_{total} is the total cost (USD).

A real discount rate consistent with prevailing power sector investment practice was applied in the economic analysis.

Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Framework

To resolve conflicts among thermodynamic, economic, and environmental objectives, a structured MCDM framework was implemented, using AHP to derive weights and WSM and TOPSIS to rank alternatives.

Decision Criteria

Five criteria were selected based on technical relevance, investment significance, and sustainability considerations. The criteria considered in this study are thermal efficiency (benefit criterion), net power output (benefit criterion), specific fuel consumption (cost criterion), emission rate (cost criterion), and installation cost (cost criterion).

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process was employed to derive relative weights of the decision criteria. A pairwise comparison matrix was constructed using Saaty’s nine-point scale, and eigenvector normalization was applied to compute criterion weights. Consistency of judgments was verified using the consistency ratio (CR), with $CR < 0.1$ considered acceptable.

Weighted Sum Method (WSM)

The normalized decision matrix is expressed as:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max(x_j)} \quad (\text{Benefit}) \quad (18)$$

Where r_{ij} is a normalized decision matrix element, x_{ij} is the performance value of alternative i under criterion j and $\max(x_j)$ is the maximum value of alternative j .

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\min(x_j)}{x_{ij}} \quad (\text{Cost}) \quad (19)$$

Where r_{ij} is a normalized decision matrix element, x_{ij} is the performance value of alternative i under criterion j and $\min(x_j)$ is the minimum value of alternative j .

The weighted score is computed as:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j r_{ij} \quad (20)$$

Where S_i is the separation distance, w_j is the weight of the criterion, n is the number of criteria and r_{ij} is a normalized decision matrix element.

TOPSIS Method

The normalized decision matrix is given by:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum x_{ij}^2}} \quad (21)$$

Where r_{ij} is a normalized decision matrix element and x_{ij} is the performance value of alternative i under criterion j .

The weighted normalized matrix is:

$$v_{ij} = w_j r_{ij} \quad (22)$$

Where v_{ij} is a weighted normalized value, w_j is the weight of the criterion and r_{ij} is a normalized decision matrix element.

The ideal and negative-ideal solutions are defined as:

$$A^+ = \langle \max v_{ij} \mid j \in J_b; \min v_{ij} \mid j \in J_c \rangle \quad (23)$$

Where A^+ is an ideal solution, $\max v_{ij}$ is the maximum weighted normalized value and $\min v_{ij}$ is the maximum weighted normalized value.

$$A^- = \langle \min v_{ij} \mid j \in J_b; \max v_{ij} \mid j \in J_c \rangle \quad (24)$$

Where A^- is negative-ideal solutions, $\max v_{ij}$ is the maximum weighted normalized value and $\min v_{ij}$ is the maximum weighted normalized value.

Separation measures are computed as:

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum (v_{ij} - A_j^+)^2} \quad (25)$$

Where D_i^+ is the ideal separation measure.

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum (v_{ij} - A_j^-)^2} \quad (26)$$

Where D_i^- is the negative-ideal separation measures.

The relative closeness coefficient is given by:

$$C_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^+ + D_i^-} \quad (27)$$

Where C_i It is a relative closeness coefficient.

Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying key operating parameters, including ambient temperature, compressor pressure ratio, turbine inlet temperature, mass flow rate, and component efficiencies, while holding other

parameters constant. The resulting variations in thermal efficiency, net power output, specific fuel consumption, heat rate, and emission rate were analysed to assess operational robustness and ranking stability.

Methodological Robustness

The integration of high-fidelity process simulation, life-cycle economic analysis, and dual MCDM techniques ensures transparency, reproducibility, and decision robustness. The use of both WSM and TOPSIS mitigates methodological bias and enhances confidence in the final retrofit selection. Furthermore, the application of real plant data significantly improves the practical relevance and credibility of the decision framework.

Results and Discussion

Thermodynamic Performance Assessment

The thermodynamic performance of the baseline gas turbine and the three retrofit configurations was evaluated using the modelling framework described in Section 2. The results clearly demonstrate that all retrofit options yield substantial improvements in overall plant performance, with notable differences in the magnitude and balance of these improvements.

Figure 2 presents the thermal efficiency of the baseline plant and the three retrofit configurations. The baseline simple-cycle gas turbine exhibits the lowest efficiency due to the absence of waste-heat recovery and its limited expansion capability. Among the retrofit options, MGTP-1 achieves the highest thermal efficiency of 47.44%, representing a significant improvement over the base configuration.

This enhancement is primarily attributed to the combined effects of exhaust gas regeneration, HRSG-based steam injection, and the additional low-pressure turbine stage. Regeneration recovers a portion of the exhaust heat to preheat compressed air, thereby reducing fuel consumption, while steam injection increases the working-fluid mass flow rate through the turbine. The additional turbine stage enables extended expansion of high-enthalpy exhaust

gases, resulting in higher energy extraction and improved cycle efficiency.

MGTP-3 also exhibits considerable efficiency gains due to its high level of thermodynamic integration. However, the marginal efficiency improvement relative to MGTP-1 is offset by increased system complexity and associated auxiliary losses. MGTP-2 demonstrates a moderate efficiency gain but is constrained by the higher fuel consumption related to dual-combustion-chamber operation. These trends are consistent with previous studies reporting that regeneration and extended expansion processes yield substantial efficiency gains, particularly under high ambient temperatures.

Figure 2. Thermal Efficiency of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Net Power Output

The net power output of all configurations is shown in Figure 3. MGTP-1 delivers the highest net power output of 157.08 MW, indicating superior power augmentation capability compared to both the baseline and other retrofit options.

The power enhancement achieved by MGTP-1 results from the synergistic interaction of inlet air cooling, steam injection, and extended turbine expansion. Inlet air cooling increases the compressor mass flow rate, steam injection augments the turbine working-fluid flow, and

the additional turbine stage converts more of the exhaust-gas enthalpy into practical shaft work. As a result, MGTP-1 achieves a higher power-to-fuel ratio than the other configurations.

MGTP-3 also achieves significant power augmentation; however, the benefits are partially offset by higher auxiliary power requirements and increased internal losses due to system complexity. MGTP-2 exhibits a minor increase in power output, reflecting the thermodynamic penalty associated with dual-combustion-chamber operation.

Figure 3. Net Power Output of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Fuel Utilization and Heat Rate

Specific fuel consumption (SFC) results are presented in Figure 4. MGTP-1 achieves the lowest SFC among all configurations, indicating superior fuel utilization efficiency. The reduction in SFC is a direct consequence of improved thermal efficiency and enhanced energy recovery through regeneration and extended expansion.

In contrast, MGTP-2 exhibits higher SFC values due to increased fuel demand required to sustain dual combustion chambers. Although MGTP-3 benefits from improved energy recovery, its higher auxiliary consumption and thermal losses result in a slightly higher SFC than that of MGTP-1.

Figure 5 presents the heat rate of the evaluated configurations. Consistent with the thermal

efficiency trends, MGTP-1 achieves the lowest heat rate, indicating the least fuel energy input per unit of electricity generated. The inverse relationship between thermal efficiency and heat rate confirms the internal consistency and validity of the simulation model.

Figure 4. SFC of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Figure 5. Heat Rate of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Emission Performance

The emission-rate results are shown in Figure 6. MGTP-1 demonstrates the lowest emission intensity due to its reduced fuel consumption per

unit of electricity generated. Although MGTP-3 achieves relatively low emission rates, its higher absolute fuel usage and system complexity diminish its environmental advantage. MGTP-2 records the highest emission rate among the retrofit options, reflecting the trade-off between combustion staging and increased fuel demand.

These results corroborate previous findings that efficiency-driven retrofit strategies provide the most effective pathway for emission reduction in gas turbine power plants, particularly in regions where fuel costs and carbon intensity are critical decision factors.

Figure 6. Emission Rate of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Economic Performance Evaluation

The economic performance of the baseline plant and retrofit configurations was assessed using a life-cycle cost-benefit analysis over a 20-year operating horizon.

Net Economic Benefit

Figure 7 presents the net economic benefit of each configuration. MGTP-1 yields the highest net benefit, at approximately USD 670 million, over the evaluation period. This superior financial performance is driven by its combination of high-power output, reduced fuel consumption, and a lower capital investment relative to MGTP-3.

MGTP-3 generates substantial revenue due to its enhanced power output; however, its higher

installation and maintenance costs reduce its overall economic attractiveness. MGTP-2 exhibits the lowest net benefit among the retrofit options, primarily due to elevated fuel expenditure and limited efficiency gains.

These results demonstrate that thermodynamic improvements alone do not guarantee economic viability and underscore the need to integrate long-term economic evaluation into retrofit decision-making.

Figure 7. Net Economic Benefit of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Benefit-Cost Ratio

The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of the evaluated configurations is shown in Figure 8. MGTP-1 achieves the highest BCR of 2.26, indicating that each dollar of investment yields more than twice the return over the plant lifetime. This strong economic performance further confirms MGTP-1 as the most financially attractive retrofit option.

Although MGTP-3 exhibits a high revenue-generating potential, its higher capital and operating costs result in a lower BCR. MGTP-2 records the lowest BCR among the retrofit options, reflecting its comparatively poor fuel economy and moderate power augmentation.

Figure 8. Benefit-Cost Ratio of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Results

While thermodynamic and economic analyses provide valuable insights, retrofit selection ultimately requires resolving trade-offs among multiple, often conflicting objectives. To address this challenge, WSM and TOPSIS were applied using AHP-derived criterion weights. 4.5.1 Weighted Sum Method (WSM)

Weighted Sum Method (WSM)

The WSM results are presented in Figure 9. MGTP-1 achieves the highest overall weighted score, followed by MGTP-3 and MGTP-2.

Figure 9. WSM Score of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

The dominance of MGTP-1 is primarily driven by its superior performance in high-weight criteria, particularly thermal efficiency, net power output, and specific fuel consumption. The results indicate that even when all criteria are considered simultaneously, MGTP-1 provides the most balanced thermo-economic and environmental performance.

TOPSIS Ranking

Figure 10 presents the relative closeness coefficients obtained from the TOPSIS analysis. Consistent with the WSM results, MGTP-1 yields the highest closeness coefficient, indicating the shortest distance to the ideal solution and the most significant separation from the negative-ideal solution.

MGTP-3 ranks second, reflecting its strong thermodynamic performance but is penalized by higher installation costs and system complexity. MGTP-2 ranks third, primarily due to higher fuel consumption and emission intensity. The strong agreement between WSM and TOPSIS rankings enhances confidence in the robustness and reliability of the decision outcome.

Figure 10. Closeness Coefficient of the Simple and Modified Gas Turbine Plants

Sensitivity Analysis and Robustness of Results

Sensitivity analysis was conducted to examine the influence of key operating parameters on the

thermodynamic performance of the baseline and retrofit configurations and to assess the robustness of the retrofit ranking under varying operating conditions. A one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) approach was adopted to isolate the marginal effect of each parameter while holding all other variables constant. This approach enables clear attribution of performance variations to individual parameters and is widely applied in steady-state gas turbine performance studies.

The parameters investigated include ambient temperature, compressor pressure ratio, turbine inlet temperature, working-fluid mass flow rate, and the isentropic efficiencies of the significant components. These parameters were selected for their strong influence on gas turbine performance and their practical relevance to real-world plant operation, particularly under tropical climatic conditions. For each parameter, values were varied within representative operating ranges consistent with manufacturer specifications, site conditions, and published literature, while maintaining identical modelling assumptions across all configurations.

Figures 11 and 12 illustrate the effect of ambient temperature on thermal efficiency and net power output, respectively.

Figure 11. Effect of Ambient Temperature on the Thermal Efficiency of the modified and straightforward gas turbine Plants

As ambient temperature increases, compressor inlet air density decreases, resulting in reduced mass flow rate, lower thermal efficiency, and a corresponding decline in net power output across all configurations. This behaviour is consistent with established gas turbine performance theory and previously reported studies. Despite the overall performance degradation, the MGTP-1 configuration consistently maintains superior thermal efficiency and net power output across the investigated temperature range. This advantage is attributed to the combined effects of inlet air cooling, exhaust gas regeneration, steam injection, and extended turbine expansion, which collectively mitigate the adverse impact of high ambient temperatures.

Figure 12. Effect of Ambient Temperature on the Net Power Output of the modified and straightforward gas turbine Plants

Similar monotonic trends were observed when varying compressor pressure ratio, turbine inlet temperature, mass flow rate, and component isentropic efficiencies. In all cases, absolute performance values changed in accordance with expected thermodynamic behaviour; however, the relative performance ordering of the retrofit configurations remained unchanged. The near-linear trends observed in the sensitivity results are a direct consequence of the steady-state modelling framework, the assumption of constant component efficiencies, and the one-

factor-at-a-time parameter variation adopted in this study. Comparable linear sensitivities over narrow operating ranges have been widely reported for industrial gas turbines under fixed-efficiency assumptions.

To evaluate decision robustness, the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and TOPSIS rankings were recomputed for all sensitivity scenarios. In every case examined, MGTP-1 remained the top-ranked retrofit option, followed by MGTP-3 and MGTP-2. This consistent ranking across all parameter variations confirms that selecting MGTP-1 is insensitive to reasonable fluctuations in operating conditions and is therefore robust from both thermodynamic and decision-making perspectives.

Overall, the sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the proposed retrofit selection is stable and reliable under realistic variations in key operating parameters. While nonlinear effects associated with parameter interactions, component degradation, variable efficiency maps, and transient or part-load operation are beyond the scope of the present steady-state analysis, these aspects represent important directions for future research.

Discussion of Key Findings

The combined thermodynamic, economic, and MCDM results clearly demonstrate that MGTP-1 represents the optimal retrofit configuration for the studied gas turbine power plant. Its superior performance arises from the synergistic integration of regeneration, steam injection, inlet air cooling, and extended turbine expansion, thereby enhancing energy utilization without excessive cost escalation.

The consistent ranking of MGTP-1 by both WSM and TOPSIS confirms that the selection is not an artifact of a single decision method but reflects a genuinely balanced compromise among competing objectives. This finding reinforces the importance of applying structured MCDM techniques in retrofit planning, particularly when decisions involve significant capital investments and long operational lifetimes.

From a practical standpoint, the proposed retrofit configuration offers a technically feasible

and economically attractive pathway for improving the performance and sustainability of aging gas turbine assets. The results provide actionable guidance for plant operators and investors seeking to enhance power output, reduce fuel costs, and mitigate environmental impact without resorting to complete plant replacement.

Conclusions

This study developed and applied an integrated thermo-economic and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) framework to identify the optimal retrofit configuration for an existing gas turbine power plant operating under conflicting performance objectives. Using the Omotosho gas turbine power plant as a real-world case study, three advanced retrofit configurations were systematically evaluated against the baseline plant through high-fidelity process simulation, life-cycle economic assessment, and structured decision analysis.

Thermodynamic modelling results demonstrate that all retrofit configurations substantially outperform the baseline simple-cycle plant in terms of thermal efficiency, net power output, fuel utilization, and emission intensity. Among the evaluated options, the MGTP-1 configuration consistently exhibited superior performance, achieving the highest thermal efficiency (47.44%), the highest net power output (157.08 MW), and the lowest specific fuel consumption. These improvements are primarily attributed to the synergistic integration of inlet air cooling, exhaust gas regeneration, HRSG-based steam injection, and extended turbine expansion, which together enhance energy recovery and reduce fuel demand without imposing excessive thermodynamic penalties.

The life-cycle economic analysis conducted over a 20-year operating horizon further confirmed the advantage of MGTP-1. This configuration yielded the highest net economic benefit and benefit–cost ratio among all retrofit alternatives, indicating that it provides the most attractive balance between capital investment and long-term financial return. Although MGTP-3 achieved comparable thermodynamic gains, its higher installation and maintenance costs reduced its overall economic competitiveness,

underscoring the need to consider performance and cost metrics in retrofit planning jointly.

To resolve trade-offs among thermodynamic, economic, and environmental objectives, a structured MCDM framework was implemented using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) for criterion weighting and both the Weighted Sum Method (WSM) and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for alternative ranking. Both methods independently identified MGTP-1 as the optimal retrofit configuration, demonstrating strong consistency and robustness of the decision outcome. The convergence of rankings across two distinct MCDM techniques confirms that the selected retrofit solution is not method-dependent but represents a genuinely balanced compromise among competing objectives.

Sensitivity analysis further demonstrated that MGTP-1 maintains its relative superiority across a wide range of operating conditions, particularly under variations in ambient temperature and key cycle parameters. This robustness is especially relevant for gas turbine operation in tropical climates, where ambient effects strongly influence plant performance, fuel costs, and profitability.

Overall, this study demonstrates that combining detailed plant-level thermo-economic modelling with structured multi-criteria decision analysis provides a robust and transparent decision-support framework for gas turbine retrofit planning. The proposed methodology moves beyond single-metric optimization and provides practical guidance for power plant operators, investors, and policymakers seeking cost-effective and environmentally sustainable strategies to enhance the performance of aging gas turbine assets.

Future Work

While the present study provides a comprehensive and practically relevant decision framework, several directions for future research are identified.

First, future studies may incorporate objective or hybrid weighting schemes, such as entropy-based, CRITIC, or fuzzy methods, to further reduce subjectivity in assessing criterion

importance and enhance decision transparency. Integrating uncertainty-aware MCDM techniques, such as fuzzy or probabilistic TOPSIS, would enable the explicit representation of uncertainties associated with cost estimation, fuel price volatility, emission factors, and long-term performance degradation.

Second, extending the modelling framework to include dynamic operational behaviour, part-load performance, and transient response would enhance the realism of retrofit evaluation, particularly for power plants operating under variable demand profiles and integrating renewable energy. Incorporating degradation and maintenance models would further enhance life-cycle performance assessment.

Third, the environmental assessment can be expanded beyond direct combustion emissions to encompass full life-cycle ecological impacts, including water consumption, material use, and embodied carbon associated with retrofit implementation. This would enable a more comprehensive sustainability-oriented evaluation aligned with emerging climate policy and decarbonization objectives.

Finally, applying the proposed framework across multiple plant locations and different gas turbine technologies would enhance its generalizability and support regional- or national-level retrofit planning strategies. Integrating carbon pricing and emissions trading mechanisms into economic evaluation would further strengthen the policy relevance of future studies.

Author Contributions

Ogbe Emmanuel Ediba conceived the study, developed the methodology, performed the thermodynamic and economic analyses, and drafted the manuscript.

Olusegun Samuel Dare implemented the multi-criteria decision-making analysis, conducted sensitivity studies, and reviewed the manuscript.

Ochogwu Emmanuel Bamaiyi assisted with modelling, data analysis, interpretation of results, and manuscript revision.

Conflicts of Interest

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix A

Figure 13. Process Flow Diagram of the Conventional Omotosho Gas Turbine Power Plant

Figure 14. Process Flow Diagram of MGTP-1.

Figure 15: Process Flow Diagram of MGTP - 2

Figure 16. Process Flow Diagram of MGTP-3